

Fishing Architecture

Oceans Shape Cities

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For over four centuries, New England's fisheries have been economically and culturally linked to ground fishing. In Gloucester, Massachusetts, Atlantic cod fishing shaped the urban landscape, with its iconic fleet of schooners anchored at the inner port wharves and large areas covered by drying racks. Cod's dominance was only challenged in the 19th century, as shifts in market demand and advancements in fish processing and storage encouraged the rise of other species — such as mackerel, herring, halibut, and haddock.

In response to these transformations, the local fishing economy evolved through the establishment of essential shore-side facilities, including sail lofts, ice houses, and cooperages. Innovations in by-product utilization reduced waste and increased profitability: fish heads and bones were converted into fertilizer, skins were repurposed into glue, and swim bladders were used for isinglass in the beverage industry. Proximity to fishing grounds and major markets like Boston further fueled Gloucester's growth, cementing its status as a major fishing center and showcasing the resilience of its industry.

The worked presented outlines ongoing research into the relationship between marine resource exploitation and Gloucester's built environment. The study follows a mixed-methods strategy, integrating Gloucester's historical timeline from 1880 to 1930 with statistical and geospatial data. Preliminary findings highlight the effectiveness of this interdisciplinary approach, revealing patterns and insights that traditional historical methods might overlook. The integration of diverse data sources provides new perspectives on the interactions between fisheries, urban development, and environmental change. This study aims to contribute to the expanding fields of digital and environmental humanities.

Keywords: Digital humanities; Environmental studies; History of fisheries; Fishing architecture; Urban development; Urban history.

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